

RATIONAL USE OF NATURAL RESOURCES OF BAKHMAL DISTRICT

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Abstract: *Through this article, we are going to explore Rational use of natural resources of Bakhmal district. Moreover, full definition of natural sources and facts about the specific features of region were given.*

Key Words: *rational, integrated nature, economic growth, Minerals, natural resources, biophysical environment.*

At present, the problem of rational and integrated nature management is given special attention by scientists from different countries. This is due to the fact that the modern approach to the analysis of factors, dynamics, problems and interpretation of economic growth - as the main goal of the country's economic development - presupposes the high importance of nature management, as well as regulation of the process of reproduction of natural resources and preservation of the quality of the natural environment. The "Concept of sustainable development" is gaining more and more popularity, reinterpreting the concepts of "growth", "economic growth", "development" and the natural environment

Natural resources refers to materials and energy in the natural world that could be used by humankind in production and in our lives (e.g. biological resources, land resources, mineral resources, water resources, climate resources, solar power resources, wind power resources, tidal power resources, etc.). Natural resources are important elements of the ecological system and constitute the environmental conditions on which humankind depends as well as the physical basis on which society depends. Our modern economic system depends increasingly on the consumption of natural resources. However, natural resources are not inexhaustible; they are also scarce. The limited reserves and uneven distribution of natural resources is in sharp contrast to the never ceasing demands of human beings, and this is the reason for the shortage of natural resources. The only way to solve the problem is for people to exploit and utilize natural resources reasonably, efficiently, and cleanly. We must therefore familiarize ourselves with the differing features of natural

resources. Renewable resources can be renewed and retrieved in the cyclic movement of the ecological system after being reasonably exploited and utilized.

Located in the center of the Eurasian continent, the Republic of Uzbekistan is bordered by Kazakhstan to the north, Turkmenistan and Afghanistan to the south, and Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan to the east. Covering 447,400 km², the territory is divided into 12 main administrative areas (oblasts) and the semi-autonomous Republic of Karakalpakstan in the northwest. With a population of 23.3 million, the country is densely populated compared with other Central Asian republics. Uzbekistan is globally and regionally important due to its location between the European, Middle Eastern, and Asian biogeographical regions. Its varying landscapes of high mountain ranges, wide steppes, deserts, riparian wetlands, and the Aral Sea has resulted in a diversity of habitats. Uzbekistan is a very important flyway for many migratory bird species between northern Europe and their wintering grounds in Africa and Asia. Almost 85 percent of Uzbekistan's territory is occupied by desert or semidesert, including the largest desert in Central Asia, the Kyzylkum. In the east and southeast, the extensive Tien-Shan and Gissar-Alai mountain systems, which occupy 15 percent of the territory, flank the deserts. The main water arteries are the transboundary rivers, the Amudarya and the Syrdarya, which used to deliver their waters into the Aral Sea, a large part of which is (or was) within Uzbekistan. These rivers have broad, flat valleys, used intensively for irrigated agriculture.

Minerals and mining also are important to Uzbekistan's economy. Gold alongside cotton, is a major foreign exchange earner, unofficially estimated at around 20% of total exports. Uzbekistan is the world's seventh-largest gold producer, mining about 80 tons per year, and holds the fourth-largest reserves in the world. Uzbekistan has an abundance of natural gas, used both for domestic consumption and export; oil used for domestic consumption; and significant reserves of copper, lead, zinc, tungsten, and uranium. Inefficiency in energy use is generally high, because the low controlled prices do not stimulate consumers to conserve energy. Uzbekistan is a partner country of the EU energy programmes, which has four key topics: enhancing energy security, convergence of member state energy markets on the basis of EU internal energy market principles, supporting sustainable energy development, and attracting investment for energy projects of common and regional interest. Uzbekistan as a country has the most extensive irrigated area and the largest population in the

Central Asian region is the most vulnerable in terms of water resources. Only about 18% of the volume needed for the country's needs water resources formed within the country where the main part is covered by resources of trans boundary rivers Amu Darya and Syr Darya. As the volume of water resources will be reduced as a result of climate change and rising consumption, coordinated management of water resources will reduce the likelihood of future conflict. From improved water use efficiency benefits everyone. Nowadays, in front of Uzbekistan stand the row of water challenges. The role of vital problems are the shortage of water resources and irrational use of them. For solution that challenges in agriculture sphere of the Republic are dealt following reforms: to inculcate water saving technologies – to use drip and sprinkling irrigation in the agricultural sewage in order to rational use of water resources.

Jizzakh is one of the important economic and social centre of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Farish, Bakhmal, Zaamin and Gallaaral districts are located in the mountains and foothills of the region. For this reason, these areas are rich in unique natural resources, one of which is natural sources. All life forms especially humans depend on their surrounding biophysical environment for their well-being and survival but due to overuse of these resources, environment has been degrading rapidly. Among these springs, water is one of the most important natural resource for humans, wildlife and the whole environment. Assessment of ambient water quality determines its use for humans and ecological purposes [1-4]. Water quality represents the purity of water and expresses the suitability of water for various uses like drinking, industrial water supply, and irrigation, propagation of aquatic organisms and generation of hydro power. The water quality is assessed in order to determine its portability, safety of human contact and ecosystem health. Poor quality of water is due to high level of organic and inorganic substance that does not fit in the standard limits given by government. Water quality indicated by various physical parameters such as pH, total solids, total dissolved solids, total suspended solids, alkalinity, free CO₂, dissolved oxygen, hardness, chlorine content, and sodium content. Nitrate contamination results from human and animal wastes, soil nitrogen content, plant debris, industrial effluents and chemicals, and seepage and drainage system . Springs described as «bowls of liquid light», are one of the most wonderful and scenic place in the nature.

Biological diversity is a vitally important resource for meeting various demands of the society, facilitating sustainable development of the country. It is an integral part of the economic and livelihood activities, and

its conservation and sustainable use are paramount to ensure crisis-free development. Biodiversity in Uzbekistan is linked with such sectors of economy that depend on natural ecosystems and their services (e.g., animal husbandry, irrigated agriculture, forestry, fishery, recreation, tourism, etc.); as well as sectors, which adversely affect biodiversity and ecosystems' functioning (e.g., oil and gas extraction, chemical industry, water resources management, waste disposal, transport infrastructure, urban development, etc.). Geographic position of Uzbekistan, diversity of physiographic conditions determine its rich biological diversity. Vast deserts of Uzbekistan, mountain steppes, forests, alpine meadows, and waterbodies are all characteristic ecosystems with typical ecological and faunistic systems. Remaining natural ecosystems of Uzbekistan help to stabilize the territories, in which the lands have lost their ability to support sustainable favorable environment due to the disturbance caused by human activities. Esthetic and recreational importance of biodiversity is very high. Attractiveness of the country from this point of view determines the development of the tourism sector. Species and ecosystem diversity make Uzbekistan attractive for scientific research and implementation of educational programmes. In this connection, it is important to include the issues of biodiversity into the process of national planning, decision-making and awareness raising of a wide range of public. Forest and wetland ecosystems and those used for pastures are worth to note among the ecosystems that are the most intensively used and that are important for social and economic development of the country and conservation of globally important biodiversity.

To sum up, throughout human evolution, and especially after the first industrial revolution in the eighteenth century, natural resources have been the physical basis for the existence and development of human beings and have helped us work wonders in social and economic development. But during this process, a large amount of natural resources are consumed and some are depleted. The unreasonable mode of exploitation has created pollution of the global environment and ecological destruction, and the momentum is continuing. All this has posed a severe threat to the subsistence and development of humankind. On this account, reasonable exploitation of natural resources and the subsistence and development of human beings are fundamentally interrelated. The importance of protecting and utilizing natural resources in a reasonable manner has gradually dawned on the world.

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